

ASTRAL

All Atlantic Ocean Sustainable, Profitable and Resilient Aquaculture

GA no **863034**

Research and Innovation Action (RIA)

Start date: 1st September 2020. End date: 30th August 2024

D 7.4 Project website and social media accounts

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Document administration

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Document history and changes

Version	Date	Author	Description
1	29/09/2020	Marine Desoche	This deliverable includes the links to the project's website and social media pages.

Evidence of accomplishment

Web-links: Astral website https://www.astral-project.eu/ Astral Facebook page https://www.facebook.com/ASTRALH2020 Astral LinkedIn page https://www.linkedin.com/company/astral-h2020project/ Astral Twitter page https://twitter.com/astral_h2020
